

Simulation of the Performance and Emission Analysis of Diesel Blend Biofuel Obtained From Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil with and without Suitable Nano Additives

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Abstract:—According to the test on a typical modern Euro 6 diesel engine conducted by the International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT), it was found that it emits 7 to 10 times more Nitrogen Dioxide than the achieved Euro 6 Test Limits (80mg/ km). In 2018, a total of 24% of global CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion came from transportation. This truly calls for the need for a lesser polluting alternative fuel in the automotive industry. After being inspired by the work done by researchers all across the globe on biodiesel, we propose the idea of synthesizing biofuels from cold-pressed hemp methyl ester. First, we conducted alkaline transesterification to produce hemp methyl ester from the cold-pressed hemp seed oil. Based on the Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS) analysis report of the hemp methyl ester from the literature, we found out the physical and chemical properties of it using BioDiesel Analyzer software. We compared the physical and chemical properties of the hemp methyl ester with diesel as per the ASTM standard D975 for diesel. We conducted the Diesel RK simulation of the performance and emission parameters of a Compression Ignition (CI) Engine test rig using diesel, pure hemp methyl ester, and diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio 80:20 by volume (B20). The performance and emission parameters obtained from the Diesel RK software are compared with that of standard diesel emissions. If higher emissions of any of the greenhouse gases are reported from the Diesel RK simulation, a suitable nano additive is proposed after an extensive critical analysis.

Keywords: *Hemp methyl ester, Diesel RK, Biodiesel Analyzer, Nanoparticle blends, Performance Analysis, Emission Tests*

1. Introduction

Biofuel is a renewable source of energy that has been derived from microbial, plant, or animal materials. They will be either in an exceedingly solid, liquid or gaseous state. The solid or liquid state of biofuels is preferred over the gaseous state as they're easier to move, deliver, and burn cleanly. Biofuels are often produced from plants or from biological wastes from agricultural, industrial, commercial sources. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has defined bioenergy as a renewable kind of energy. Biofuels are of two types. They're as follows:

- I. Bioethanol
- II. Biodiesel

Bioethanol is alcohol obtained from the fermentation of the carbohydrates produced in sugar or starch crops. Cellulosic biomass from non-food sources also can be used to produce bioethanol. Ethanol may be used directly in vehicles in their purest form but it's generally blended with gasoline to extend octane and improve vehicle emissions. Biodiesel is obtained from oils or fats by the transesterification process. It can be used in its purest form in automobiles but generally, it's blended with diesel to reduce the levels of Greenhouse Gas Emissions. Biofuels are classified into gaseous biofuel and liquid biofuel based on their state of matter. Syngas, biogas and biomethane fall under the gaseous biofuel category. Ethanol, methanol, butanol, biodiesel, green diesel, straight vegetable oil, and bioethers fall under the liquid biofuel category. The advantages of biofuels are as follows:

- I. Carbon neutral nature of the biofuel as a source of energy.
- II. Large positive impact on the air quality due to the usage of biofuels.
- III. Low area-specific power density.

The research paper titled "Introduction of Biodiesel as a Sustainable Resource" by Sylvia Adipah (Sylvia Adipah, 2018), explains the importance of biodiesel as a sustainable source of energy. Bioenergy can be used as biofuel for transport as well as biomass for heat and electricity production. The various advantages of biodiesel like its renewable nature, economical benefit, creation of a pro-agriculture economy, and the positive impact on the environment have been highlighted. The research paper titled "Production methods of biodiesel" by A. Rajalingam, S. P. Jani, A. Senthil Kumar, and M. Adam Khan (A. Rajalingam *et al*, 2016), explains the commonly used biodiesel production methods like direct use and blending, transesterification process, pyrolysis, and microemulsion. The study concluded that the transesterification process will give a better fuel quality and yield efficiency and there is no requirement for any special equipment. The review article titled "A critical review on production of biodiesel from various feedstocks" by Deepak Verma, Janmit Raj, Amit Pal, and Manish Jain (Deepak Verma *et al*, 2016) contains the work of past researchers published between 2005 and 2015 on producing biodiesel from edible oil, non-edible oil, and waste cooking oil. Transesterification is a commonly employed method for biodiesel production. The purpose of this method is to reduce the viscosity of oil or fat using acid or base catalyst in the presence of methanol or ethanol. Transesterification with an alkali catalyst (KOH and NaOH) is more economical than an acid catalyst and enzyme catalyst. Biodiesel production is strongly affected by parameters such as the molar ratio of alcohol, reaction temperature, reaction time, and catalyst concentration. The research paper titled "Conversion of Waste Cooking Oil to Biodiesel" by Rummi Devi Saini (Rummi Devi Saini, 2017) highlights the harm caused by recycling the waste cooking oil. The study suggests a synthesis of biodiesel from waste cooking oil. The transesterification process is commonly employed for its formation. Heterogeneous catalysts are recommended as the best catalysts in biodiesel production. In the research paper titled "Esterification and transesterification over SrO-ZnO/Al₂O₃ as a novel bifunctional catalyst for biodiesel production" by Ali Al-Saadi, Bobby Mathan, Yinghe He (Ali Al-Saadi *et al*, 2020), the team synthesized a novel bifunctional catalyst by loading metal (Zn) and alkali metal (Sr) on alumina oxide using the wet impregnation method and evaluated the efficiency of the synthesized catalyst under mild reaction conditions. A series of SrO-ZnO/Al₂O₃

catalysts were prepared for esterification and transesterification purposes. The research paper titled “Long term activity of modified ZnO nanoparticles for transesterification” by Shuli Yan, Siddharth Mohan, Craig DiMaggio, Manhoe Kim, K.Y. Simon Ng, Steven O. Salley(Shuli Yan *et al*,2010) studied the conversion of Crude algae oil, corn oil from DDGs, crude palm oil, crude soybean oil, crude coconut oil, waste cooking oil, food-grade soybean oil, and food-grade soybean oil with 3% water and 5% Free Fatty Acid addition were converted into biodiesel within 3 hours using modified ZnO nanoparticles. The review paper titled “A review on biodiesel production, combustion, emissions and performance” by Syed AmeerBasha, K. Raja Gopal, S. Jebaraj(Syed Ameer Basha,2009)explains the work by 130 scientists in the biofuel domain between 1980 and 2008 in the domain of biodiesel production, combustion and emission performance analysis. The majority of the scientists reported that short-term engine tests using vegetable oils as fuels were very promising. On the other hand, the long-term test results showed higher carbon built-up and lubricating oil contamination resulting in engine failure. They concluded that vegetable oils, either chemically altered or blended with diesel to prevent engine failure. The research paper titled “Comparative study of Hemp and Jatropha oil blends used as an alternative fuel in diesel engine” by Prashant Gill, S.K Soni, K.Kundu(Prashant Gill *et al*,2011) compared the performance and emission characteristics of different blends of transesterified Hemp (B10 and B20)and Jatropha (B10 and B20) biodiesel was done on a 550 cm³ single-cylinder four-stroke water-cooled diesel engine and the results were compared to that of diesel. Methyl ester of Hemp oil results in a slightly increased thermal efficiency as compared to that of diesel and Jatropha oil. CO₂ and CO emission were low at higher loads with methyl ester of Hemp oil as compared to methyl esters of Jatropha oil. NO_x emission was significantly increased with methyl ester of Hemp oil compared to diesel and Jatropha methyl ester. There is a higher emission of NO_x Hemp Methyl Esters blended with diesel than the ASTM standard. The research paper titled “Brown hemp methyl ester: Transesterification process and evaluation of fuel properties” by S.S. Ragit, S.K. Mohapatra, Prashant Gill, K. Kundu(S.S Ragit *et al*,2013) analyzed various parameters like molar ratio, catalyst concentration, and reaction time were analyzed to standardize the alkaline homogenous transesterification process of the hemp seed oil with the highest yield with the lowest possible viscosity. The maximum hemp methyl ester recovery was 93.89% with a kinematic viscosity of 2.367 cSt and at 1.13 cSt the hemp methyl ester recovery was 90.625%. The research paper titled “Physicochemical Analysis of Hemp Oil Biodiesel: A Promising Non-Edible New Source for Bioenergy” by M. Ahmad, K. Ullah, M. A. Khan, M. Zafar, M. Tariq, S. Ali & S. Sultana(M. Ahmad *et al*,2011) proved that a Biodiesel yield of 75.90 % has been obtained for a 0.67% concentration of Potassium Hydroxide(KOH) Catalyst at a molar ratio of 6:1 at 60 °C and a yield of 14.42% for 0.34% concentration of Sodium Hydroxide(NaOH).The research paper titled “Estimation of fuel properties and characterization of hemp biodiesel using spectrometric techniques” by CijilBiju John, Antony Raja Solamalai, RanjithaJambulingam&DeepanrajBalakrishnan(CijilBiju John *et al*,2020)crude hemp oil is used to produce biofuels using two-stage base-catalyzed transesterification. The estimation of fuel properties, along with the various spectrometric techniques like Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectrometry (FTIR), and Thermogravimetry-Differential Scanning Calorimetry/Derivative Thermogravimetry (TG-DSC/DTG) were used to characterize the Crude Hemp Oil Biofuel. In the research paper titled “, Methanolysis And Ethanolysis Of Raw Hemp Oil: Biodiesel Production And Fuel Characterization” by Ragit S. S, Mohapatra S. K, Kundu K, Karmakar R(Ragit S. S *et al*,2013) proceed that Methanol is more suitable for the Alkaline Homogenous Transesterification Of Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil over Ethanol for a better yield of biofuels.In this research paper titled “Biofuels production from weed biomass using nanocatalyst technology” by Safdar Ali, ObaidullahShafique, ShahidMahmood, Tariq Mahmood, Bashir Ahmad Khan, Ijaz Ahmad(Safdar Ali *et al*,2020) the undesired biomass(i.e Weed) is used to produce biofuels through nanocatalysts enhanced gasification and process. bio-gas, bio-diesel, and bio-char from mixed weed biomass of weeds like Carthamousoxyacantha, Asphodelustenuifolius, and Chenopodium album through gasification process using nanomaterials as catalysts. The research paper titled “ The Experimental Investigation

on Performance and Emission Characteristics of a Single Cylinder Diesel Engine using Nano Additives in Diesel and Biodiesel “ by K. Ramarao, C. J. Rao and D. Sreeramulu(K. Ramarao *et al*,2015) was to determine the engine performance and emissions of a single-cylinder Direct Injection (DI) diesel engine using diesel-biodiesel blends with nano additive. In this study, cottonseed oil is used to produce biofuel and blended with diesel at standard proportions. The results obtained show lower fuel consumption, better performance, and lower emissions of Carbon Monoxide (CO), Hydrocarbons (HC) but higher emissions of (NO_x), in comparison to neat diesel fuel. The research paper titled “Effect of nanoparticle on emission and performance characteristics of biodiesel” by J. B. Sajin, GokulOmanakuttanPillai, MadhavKesavapillai&SajiVarghese(J.B.Sajin *et al*,2019) proved that inclusion of 20 nm particle size of ZnO nanoparticle in M100 improves the overall combustion process and promotes a lower level of smoke emissions, carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbon (HC), and oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) emissions. The inclusion of 40 nm particle size of ZnO nanoparticle in M100 further reduces the NO_x, HC, CO, and smoke emission by 4.1%, 2.89%, 3.69%, and 3.58%, respectively, at all load conditions than neat biodiesel. The research paper titled “Performance enhancement using graphene Quantum dot and ethanol diesel blend” by Aram Heidari-Malenia, TarahomMesriGundoshmiana, Ahmad Jahanbakhshiaand BaratGhobadianb(Aram Heidari-Malenia *et al*,2020) proved that by adding GQD nanoparticles to fuel increased power and torque by 28.18% and 12.42% respectively and reduced SFC, CO and UHC by 14.35%, 29.54% and 31.12% respectively, compared to D100 fuel. The research paper titled “Experimental Investigation on Performance of a Compression Ignition Engine Fueled with Waste Cooking Oil Biodiesel–Diesel Blend Enhanced with Iron-Doped Cerium Oxide Nanoparticles” by MeshackHawi, Ahmed Elwardany, Mohamed Ismail and Mahmoud Ahmed (MeshackHawi *et al*,2019) proved to reduce the harmful emissions of diesel engines including oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) and soot.

2. Problem Formulation

The Greenhouse Gas emission numbers seem to be quite large and have an impeccably negative impact on the environment. This truly calls for the need for less polluting and a renewable source of energy to power the transportation sector. Suitable additives must be added to the diesel to reduce the Greenhouse Gas Emission. The aim of the project is to produce biodiesel from cold-pressed hemp seed oil using an alkaline homogenous transesterification process. The physical, chemical, and thermal properties of the biodiesel would be characterized using suitable tools and techniques. The performance and emission parameters of pure hemp methyl ester and diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio 80:20 by volume are found out using a test rig simulation software. The results are compared with that of a test rig using conventional diesel. If the emission parameters from the pure hemp methyl ester and diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio 80:20 by volume are found to be high, suitable adsorbents would be found out by theoretical analysis.

3. Methodology and Materials Used

To execute the proposed solution, we have decided to follow a stepwise procedure. The steps involved in the execution of the project are as follows. They are as follows:

(Step 1)Procurement Of The Required Materials: One liter of cold-pressed hemp seed oil and half a liter of Anhydrous Methanol from Vasa Scientific has been procured.

(Step 2) Alkaline Homogenous Transesterification Process: The Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil and Methanol are taken in the ratio 6:1 molar ratio and mixed with a suitable amount of anhydrous KOH. Preheating conditions of 60-degree Celsius are maintained and reaction duration of 45 mins.

(Step 3) Analysis Of Physical And Chemical Properties Of Hemp Methyl Ester: From the literature survey, the composition of the hemp-methyl ester is found out. The percentage composition of each organic acid is obtained and these values are fed into the Biodiesel Analyzer Software. From the software, the following values are obtained. They are as follows:

- I. Saturated Fatty Acids
- II. Monounsaturated Fatty Acids
- III. Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids
- IV. Degree Of Unsaturation
- V. Saponification Value,
- VI. Iodin Value
- VII. Cetane Value
- VIII. Long Chain Saturated Factor
- IX. Cold Filter Plugging Point
- X. Cloud Point
- XI. Allylic Position Equivalents
- XII. Bis-Allylic Position Equivalents
- XIII. Oxidation Stability
- XIV. Higher Heating value
- XV. Kinematic Viscosity
- XVI. Density

(Step 4) The Performance Analysis and Emission Test On Diesel RK Software: The hemp methyl ester blended with diesel is put to test in a virtual Compression Ignition Engine Test Rig provided by the Diesel RK Software. The parameters like compression ratio, stroke length, bore dia and other test rig design parameters are specified. From the above software one can obtain the performance and emission parameters. Diesel RK Software to simulate the performance and emission characteristics of the fuel on a Kirloskar TAF 1 engine. The engine has one cylinder and the combustion chamber is of hemispherical open type. The engine works on a four-stroke diesel cycle and uses direct injection. The engine is air-cooled. It has a bore dia of 85.5 mm and a stroke length of 110 mm. The engine has a displacement volume of 661 cubic-centimeters and a compression ratio of 17.5:1. It has a rated output of 4.4 kW at 1500 rpm. Parameters like Brake Power (kW), Brake Mean Effective Pressure (bar), Torque (Nm), Mass Fluid (g), Specific Fuel Consumption (kg/kWh), Brake Thermal Efficiency, Indicated Mean Effective Pressure (bar), Indicated Efficiency, Friction Mean Effective Pressure (bar), Mechanical Efficiency, Bosch Smoke Number (BOSCH), Carbon Dioxide Emission (g/kWh) and Fraction Of Wet NO_x In Exhaust Gas (ppm).

(Step 5) Critical Analysis Of The Impact On The Performance And Emission Analysis Of A Compression Ignition Engine Due To Nano Additives Blended With Biofuels: In this step, would be critically analyzing the research work done to understand the impact on the performance and emission parameters of CI Engine due to nano additives blended with the biofuels.

The entire step-by-step process can be explained using the flowchart as shown below.

Fig 1: The Flowchart Of The Execution of The Proposed Solution

The following materials were used in the alkaline homogenous transesterification process. They are as follows:

- I. Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil
- II. Methanol
- III. Anhydrous Potassium Hydroxide

We had various choices between edible and non-edible oils. The choices in the edible oils were palm oil, soybean oil, rapeseed oil, sunflower seed oil, peanut oil, cottonseed oil, palm kernel oil, coconut oil, and olive oil. On the other hand, non-edible oils like hemp seed oil, acid oil, castor oil, karanji oil, Kusum oil, mahua oil, residue oil, rice bran non-edible oil, sludge oil, and neem oil. We chose non-edible oil to synthesize the biodiesel as it is more feasible. Using edible oils to produce biodiesel can cause a shortage of edible oil resources for daily consumer use. One amongst the non-edible oils, we chose cold-pressed hemp seed oil because of its high oleic acid content and hemp can be grown on an infertile land as well. We chose cold-pressed hemp seed oil because it contains only pure hemp oil without any additives. We chose to use methanol because methanol is more suitable for the Alkaline Homogenous Transesterification Of Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil over Ethanol for a better yield of biofuels. Reaction duration plays a vital role in determining the yield. We chose to use Anhydrous Potassium Hydroxide because KOH being used as a base catalyst over NaOH can provide a good yield for the biofuel from the cold-pressed hemp seed oil.

4. Transesterification Process

The transesterification process is a reversible reaction and is applied by mixing the reactants – fatty acids, alcohol, and catalyst. A powerful base or a robust acid is used as a catalyst. The glycerol may also be used as a substrate for anaerobic digestion. There are three methods of converting oil to fatty esters. They are as follows:

- I. Base-catalyzed transesterification
- II. Acid-catalyzed transesterification,
- III. Acid Catalysis of oils to esters

We chose to use Base-catalyzed transesterification because of the following reasons. They are:

- I. Low temperature and pressure conditions are required to conduct the experiment.
- II. A yield greater than nearly 98% can be obtained.
- III. It is a simple direct conversion without any intermediate steps.
- IV. The above-cited process requires commonly used chemicals and a simple setup.

We conducted the homogenous alkaline transesterification process at the Chemistry Lab in the Department of Chemistry at Ramaiah Institute of Technology, Bangalore. The Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil and Methanol are taken in the ratio 6:1 molar ratio and mixed with a suitable amount of anhydrous KOH. Preheating conditions of 60-degree Celsius are maintained and reaction duration of 45 mins. We obtained a yield of 35 grams of Hemp Methyl Ester from 50g of Cold Pressed Hemp Seed Oil. We obtained a yield of 70% in our first attempt to synthesize hemp methyl ester.

Fig 2: Hemp Methyl Ester Obtained Before Cleaning and Drying

5. Simulation Softwares and Steps Involved

In order to execute the work, we decided to use two simple student software available to execute the project. They are as follows:

- I. BioDiesel Analyzer (Ahmad Farhad Talebi et al, 2014)
- II. Diesel RK (Diesel RK)

The above two software were chosen because of their versatility and ease of operation.

5.1 BioDiesel Analyzer

From the Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS) analysis of the Hemp Methyl Ester from various research papers to obtain the percentage composition of each organic acid in it. We used the following steps to obtain parameters like Saturated Fatty Acids, Monounsaturated Fatty Acids, Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids, Degree Of Unsaturation, Saponification Value, Iodin Value, Cetane Value, Long Chain Saturated Factor, Cold Filter Plugging Point, Cloud Point, Allylic Position Equivalents, Bis-Allylic Position Equivalents, Oxidation Stability, Higher Heating value, Kinematic Viscosity and Density. The steps are:

- (Step 1)** Install the BioDiesel Analyzer Software on your computer.
(Step 2) Open the BioDiesel Analyzer Software.
(Step 3) Enter the percentage composition of the organic acids in the hemp methyl ester.

Unselect All	Select All	Define Free Fatty Acid Profile and their corresponding percentages												
☐ C14:0	☐ C15:0	☒ C16:0	☒ C16:1	☒ C18:0	☒ C18:1	☒ C18:2	☐ C18:3	☐ C18:4	☒ C20:0	☒ C20:1	☐ C20:4	☒ C22:0	☐ C22:2	☐ C22:6
Butyric acid	Palmitic acid	5.72	Arachidic acid	0.89	Hexanoic acid	Palmitoleic acid	0.05	Eicosenoic acid	0.31	Caprylic acid	Margaric acid		Arachidonic acid	
Capric acid	Stearic acid	2.68	Behenic acid	0.19	Lauroic acid	Oleic acid	33.22	gadolenic acid		Tridecylic acid	Linoleic acid	55.53	Docosahexaenoic acid	
Mystic acid	Linolenic acid		Lignocenic acid		Pentadecanoic acid	Stearidonic acid		Nervonic acid						

Continue >>

Fig 3: The percentage composition of each organic acid in the Hemp Methyl Ester

- (Step 4)** Click on continue after entering the percentage composition of each organic acid in the hemp methyl ester.

Unsaturation Level	Cetane Number	Cold Flow Properties	Oxidation Stability	Higher Heating Value	Kinematic Viscosity	Density	Full Report	How to cite
Saturated Fatty Acids (SFA)	9.48	Cold Filter Plugging Point (CFPP) (°C)	-6.77	Cloud point (CP) (°C)	-1.98			
Monounsaturated Fatty Acids (MUFA)	33.58	Allylic Position Equivalents (APE)	144.28	Bis-Allylic Position Equivalents (BAPE)	57.31			
Polysaturated Fatty Acids (PUFA)	55.53	Oxidation Stability (OS) (hours)	0	Higher Heating Value (HHV)	38.92			
Degree of Unsaturation (DU)	144.64	Kinematic Viscosity (ν) (mm ² /s)	1.28	Density (ρ) (g/cm ³)	0.86			
Saponification Value (SV)	197.13							
Iodine Value (IV)	130.76							
Cetane Number (CN)	44.57							
Long-Chain Saturated Factor (LCSF)	3.09							

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Fig 4: The Physical And Chemical Properties Of Hemp Methyl Ester

5.2 Diesel RK

To conduct the combustion, performance, and emission analysis; we decided to use the Diesel RK software. We chose to conduct the test on a Kirloskar TAF 1 engine. The engine has one cylinder and the combustion chamber is of hemispherical open type. The engine works on a four-stroke diesel cycle and uses direct injection. The engine is air-cooled. It has a bore dia of 85.5 mm and a stroke length of 110 mm. The engine has a displacement volume of 661 cubic- centimeters and a compression ratio of 17.5:1. It has a rated output of 4.4 kW at 1500 rpm.

The steps used to conduct the combustion, performance, and emission analysis are as follows:

(Step 1) Install Diesel RK from the official website.

(Step 2) Click on the Diesel RK icon to open the software.

(Step 3) Enter the parameters that are required like the cylinder bore, piston stroke, compression ratio, engine speed, and the number of cylinders. Then click the OK button.

Fig 5: Dialog Box To Enter The General Parameters Of The Engine

(Step 4) The physical, chemical and thermal properties of the fuel are entered. Then click on the OK button.

Fig 6: The Dialog Box To Enter The Physical, Chemical And Thermal Properties Of The Fuel

(Step 5) Enter the injection profile and other parameters in the Fuel Injection & Combustion Chamber dialogue box. Then click on the OK button.

Fig 7: The Fuel Injection & Combustion Chamber Dialog Box.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Discussion Based On The Results Obtained From The BioDiesel Analyzer Software

We will be comparing our results with the properties as per the ASTM standard D975 for diesel (ASTM standard D975). The cetane number of the hemp methyl ester that we have obtained is 44.57 while the standard values for the diesel range from 40 to 55. The cetane number of the hemp methyl ester that we have obtained falls in the diesel range and not in the biodiesel range. The density of the diesel as per the specified standard is 850.768 kg/m³. The density of the hemp methyl ester that we have obtained has a density of 860 kg/m³, which is slightly higher than the specified density values for diesel. The cloud point for the diesel as per the specified standard ranges from -35 degrees celsius to 5 degrees celsius. We have obtained a value of -1.98 degrees celsius which lies within the standard range for diesel. The kinematic viscosity of the diesel as per the specified standards ranges from 1.3 mm²/s to 4.1 mm²/s. We have obtained a kinematic viscosity of 1.28 mm²/s which is very much close to the specified range of the standard. After comparing the Hemp Methyl Ester properties with the diesel parameter according to the ASTM D975, we can conclude that the hemp methyl ester is a suitable replacement for diesel. The properties can be improved by suitable blending with diesel.

Sl Number	Parameters	Values
1	Saturated Fatty Acids	9.48
2	Monounsaturated Fatty Acids	33.58
3	Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids	55.53
4	Degree Of Unsaturation	144.64
5	Saponification Value	197.13
6	Iodin value	130.76
7	Cetane Value	44.57
8	Long Chain Saturated Factor	3.09
9	Cold Filter Plugging Point	-6.77 °C
10	Cloud Point	-1.98 °C
11	Allylic Position Equivalents	144.28
12	Ba-Allylic Position Equivalents	57.31
13	Oxidation Stability	0 hours
14	Kinematic Viscosity	1.28 mm ² /s
15	Density	0.86 g/cm ³
16	Higher Heating Value	39.92

Table 1: The Values Obtained From The BioDiesel Analyzer Software

6.2 Discussion Based On The Performance Analysis And Emission Analysis Results Obtained From The Diesel RK Software

The values obtained from the Diesel RK Software have been tabulated in Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4. With the obtained values, a bar graph has been comparing the Specific Fuel Consumption(SFC), Brake Thermal Efficiency, Smoke Emission, Carbon Dioxide Emission and Oxides of Nitrogen Emission with increasing brake power diesel, Hemp Methyl Ester, Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume from the Diesel RK software. Brake power is measured in kiloWatt. Specific Fuel Consumption(SFC) is defined as the ratio of fuel consumption per unit time to the power developed by the engine. The lower the SFC value, the greater the efficiency of the engine. From the graph plotted between Brake Power and SFC(Fig 8), it is clear that with the increase in brake power more fuel is being consumed by the engine in the case of pure hemp methyl ester. While the Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume and the conventional diesel nearly have the same SFC value. From the graph, we can conclude that blending biodiesel with diesel can suitably reduce the SFC and thereby improve the efficiency of the engine. From the graph(Fig 9), it is clear that for all the test fuels, the brake thermal efficiency is increasing with a rise in Brake Power. Higher BTE means higher efficiency in conversion of the heat energy to work. This is due to a fall in heat loss and an increase in power with an increase in load. Initially, at a lower load, the BTE of the biofuel blend and hemp methyl ester is lower as compared to that of the conventional diesel. At a higher Brake Power, the BTE of the Diesel Blended Biofuel(B20) and Pure Hemp Methyl Ester is greater than that of the conventional diesel. From the above results, we can conclude that Diesel Blended Biofuel(B20) and Pure Hemp Methyl Ester are beneficial fuels in engines with higher load and also have a very good heat-to-work conversion efficiency. Bosch Smoke Number is a measuring unit used to express the smoke characteristic of the exhaust gas obtained using a Bosch smoke meter. From the graph BP v/s Smoke Emission(Fig 10), we can see that the smoke emitted from a test rig using pure hemp methyl ester or diesel blended with hemp methyl ester is less than that of a test rig using conventional diesel. In a comparison between pure hemp methyl ester and diesel blended with hemp methyl ester, the latter is a better option in terms of smoke emission. Using hemp methyl ester as fuel might affect the performance parameters.

Therefore diesel blended with hemp methyl ester is a better option as an eco-friendly fuel. From the graph BP v/s Carbon Dioxide Emission(Fig11), it's quite clear that Carbon Dioxide emissions from a test rig pure hemp methyl ester and Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume are lesser than the carbon dioxide emissions from a test rig using diesel as fuel. The presence of polyunsaturated fatty acids and monounsaturated fatty acids in the pure hemp methyl ester along with the hydrocarbons in the diesel is responsible for the generation of higher carbon dioxide emission from the test rig using diesel blended with hemp methyl ester as compared to that of a test rig only using pure hemp methyl ester. From the above graph, it's quite clear that Carbon Dioxide emissions from a test rig pure hemp methyl ester and Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume are lesser than the carbon dioxide emissions from a test rig using diesel as fuel. The presence of polyunsaturated fatty acids and monounsaturated fatty acids in the pure hemp methyl ester along with the hydrocarbons in the diesel is responsible for the generation of higher carbon dioxide emission from the test rig using diesel blended with hemp methyl ester as compared to that of a test rig only using pure hemp methyl ester. From the graph BP v/s NOxEmission(Fig 12), it is clear that the NOx emission from a test rig using diesel blended with hemp methyl ester has the lower NOx as compared to that of a test rig using pure hemp methyl ester. The test rig using diesel as the fuel has the least NOx

emission as compared to the other two test fuels. The hemp methyl ester is rich in oxygen as compared to diesel. The NO_x emission is proportional to the amount of oxygen content in biodiesel.

Brake Power (KW)	BME P (bar)	TORQUE (Nm)	MASS OF FUEL (g)	SFC kg/kwh	BTFE	IMEP (bar)	ETA-INDICATED	FMEP (bar)	ETA-MECH	BOSCH SMOKE NUMBER (BOSCH)	CO2 (g/kWh)	NO _x (PPM)
3.0614	3.878	19.491	0.025	0.36748	0.2278	5.4338	0.31924	1.2419	0.7574	5.2810	1184.1	429.6
2.8623	3.626	18.223	0.0225	0.35373	0.2367	5.1744	0.33777	1.233	0.7462	4.9954	1139.8	356.6
2.5522	3.233	16.249	0.02	0.35264	0.2374	4.7756	0.35071	1.221	0.7259	4.7067	1136.6	285.4
2.0816	2.637	13.253	0.0175	0.37832	0.2213	4.1785	0.35069	1.2048	0.6864	4.4462	1219	211.5
1.6068	2.035	10.23	0.015	0.4201	0.1993	3.5576	0.34835	1.1891	0.6312	4.1444	1353.7	163.3

Table 2: Performance And Emission Parameters Of Diesel Obtained From Diesel RK Software

Brake Power (KW)	BMEP (bar)	TORQUE (Nm)	MASS OF FUEL (g)	SFC kg/kwh	BTFE	IMEP (bar)	ETA-INDICATED	FMEP (bar)	ETA-MECH	BOSCH SMOKE NUMBER (BOSCH)	CO2 (g/kWh)	NO _x (PPM)
3.2973	4.1767	20.993	0.02500	0.34119	0.24595	5.7379	0.33789	1.2472	0.7700	5.0831	975.55	899.74
2.8692	3.6345	18.267	0.0225	0.35288	0.2378	5.1825	0.3391	1.2319	0.7469	4.865	1009	781
2.3747	3.0081	15.119	0.02	0.37899	0.22142	4.5445	0.3345	1.2148	0.7123	4.6588	1083.6	663.68
2.0597	2.6091	13.114	0.0175	0.38233	0.21948	4.1413	0.3484	1.2028	0.6845	4.3618	1093.2	542.41
1.5631	1.98	9.9517	0.015	0.43184	0.19432	3.4979	0.3433	1.1854	0.6255	4.1562	1234.7	408.04

Table 3: Performance And Emission Parameters Of Hemp Methyl Ester Obtained From Diesel RK Software

Brake Power (kW)	BMEP (bar)	TORQUE (Nm)	MASS OF FUEL (g)	SFC kg/kWh	BTFE	IMEP (bar)	ETA-INDICATED	FMEP (bar)	ETA-MECH	BOSCH SMOKE NUMBER (BOSCH)	CO ₂ (g/kWh)	NO _x (PPM)
3.1106	3.9402	19.804	0.025	0.36167	0.2316	5.4970	0.3231	1.2427	0.76024	5.2403	1111.8	586.33
2.9641	3.7546	18.871	0.0225	0.3416	0.2452	5.3065	0.3466	1.2351	0.75247	4.9274	1050.1	499.3
2.5656	3.2499	16.344	0.02	0.3508	0.2387	4.7925	0.3521	1.2209	0.72692	4.6732	1078.4	408.6
2.0904	2.6479	13.309	0.175	0.3767	0.2223	4.1811	0.3511	1.2045	0.68734	4.4146	1158.1	316.57
1.612	2.0419	10.236	0.015	0.4187	0.2000	3.5662	0.3494	1.1888	0.63204	4.1168	1287.2	243.39

Table 4: Performance And Emission Parameters Of Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume Obtained From Diesel RK Software

Fig 8:BP v/s SFC

Fig 9:BP v/s BTE

Fig 10:BP v/s Smoke Emission

Fig 11:BP v/s Carbon Dioxide Emission

Fig 12: BP v/s NO_x Emission

7. Critical Analysis Of The Impact On The Performance And Emission Analysis Of A Compression Ignition Engine Due To Nano Additives Blended With Biofuels

From the performance and emission analysis reports obtained from Diesel RK software, it's clear that better performance parameters are obtained from a test rig using pure hemp methyl ester as compared to that of a rig using conventional diesel or Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume. From the emission analysis results from the Diesel RK software, It's clear that the NO_x emissions, smoke emission, and Carbon dioxide emission are higher for a test rig pure hemp methyl ester and Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume. From the above two observations, despite having excellent performance we can say that pure hemp methyl ester is not a suitable replacement for conventional diesel because of its high NO_x, Carbon dioxide, and Smoke emission. On the other hand, Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume can be a suitable replacement for diesel because of its balance in parameter both performance and emission analysis. In order to reduce the NO_x emission and CO₂ emissions to a value lesser than that of a conventional diesel emission, we understood the need for nano additives to be added with Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume. We went through a few research papers where satisfactory emission and performance results were obtained after blending with suitable nanoparticles. The steps involved in blending nanoparticles to the hemp methyl ester are as follows:

1. A suitable nanoparticle with a diameter not exceeding 50 nm is selected.
2. Check for agglomeration and size under an electron microscope to see if it is not homogeneous for proper processing.
3. Additives are dissolved in 30ml of ethanol and kept in an ultrasonicator for 10 minutes under 24hz. Agglomerates settle down at the bottom when the solution is centrifuged at 5000rpm for 15 minutes. Monodispersed solution on the top is carefully separated from larger agglomerates settling at the bottom.
4. The presence of ethanol is removed by rotary evaporation. Nanoparticles are now free from agglomerates.
5. Nanoparticles obtained are tested in SEM to check for their reduced aggregation levels. Homogeneous nanoparticles of required ppm are mixed with a prepared biodiesel blend. They are added at certain intervals of time to avoid settling.
6. CTAB(Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide), a common positively charged surfactant for nanoparticle synthesis, is added as a coating.
7. The magnetic stirrer is set at 800 rpm which amplifies the extent of dissolution of nanoparticles and the surfactant in the biodiesel blends during the ultrasonication process.

In the paper titled “ Experimental investigations on the performance characteristics of CI engine fuelled with cerium oxide nanoparticle added biodiesel-diesel blends.” by K. Kalaimurugan, S. Karthikeyan, M. Periyasamy, G. Mahendran(K. Kalaimurugan *et al*,2020); the researchers have blended biodiesel obtained from neochlorisoleoabundans algae oil and blended it with diesel. The diesel and biodiesel obtained from neochlorisoleoabundans algae oil were blended in the ratio of 80:20 by volume. Cerium Oxide nanoparticles in a dosage of 25 ppm, 50 ppm, 75 ppm, and 100 ppm were added to the diesel, and biodiesel was obtained from neochlorisoleoabundans algae oil were blended in the ratio of 80:20 by volume. The performance and emission parameters for each dosage were found out using a Kirloskar 661 cc single-cylinder test rig. The calorific value and kinematic viscosity of the CeO₂ nano additive fuel blends were better than that of the diesel and biodiesel obtained from neochlorisoleoabundans algae oil were blended in the ratio of 80:20 by volume. The lowering Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC) may be due to the good impact of nanoparticles on the physical characteristics of fuel. The nanoparticles also have also

increased the Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE) values. In the research paper titled “Experimental Investigations on the Effects of Cerium Oxide Nanoparticle Fuel Additives on Biodiesel” by V. Sajith, C. B. Sobhan, and G. P. Peterson (V. Sajith *et al*, 2010); the researchers have obtained biodiesel from jatropha oil. It was doped with Cerium Oxide nanoparticles of the size nanoparticles of size 10 to 20 nanometers and the dosage of Cerium Oxide nanoparticles varied from 20 ppm, 40 ppm, and 80 ppm. The major physicochemical properties and the performance parameters were found out as a part of the experimentation. The flash increased linearly with the increase in the dosage of the cerium oxide nanoparticles with the jatropha biodiesel. There was an exponential decrease in the kinematic viscosity with an increase in the dosage of the cerium oxide with jatropha biodiesel. A maximum increase of 1.5% in the brake thermal efficiency was found experimentally when the dosing level was varied from 20 to 80 ppm. An average reduction of 25% to 40% in the hydrocarbon emissions was obtained for additive dosing levels ranging from 40 to 80 ppm of the additive. An average reduction of around 30% was found to occur with a dosage level of 80 ppm nanoparticles with the jatropha oil. In the paper titled "Nanoparticles as an additive in biodiesel on the working characteristics of a DI diesel engine" by A. Prabu (A. Prabu, 2018); the researchers have blended biodiesel obtained from Jatropha and blended with diesel. At 30 ppm alumina (Al₂O₃) and 30 ppm cerium oxide (CeO₂) at B20 and B100 blends were made. A single-cylinder, four-stroke DI diesel engine was employed for the test. Results obtained showed the lower heat release rate and cylinder pressure at full load condition. NO_x was reduced by 30%. At the maximum of 60% reduction of CO, 44% reduction of UBHC, and 38% reduction of smoke opacity are observed for B20A30C30 test fuel due to the improved Oxidation Reduction process by the addition of nanoparticles. Altogether, the performance, combustion, and emission characteristics of a DI diesel engine are improved by the incorporation of alumina and cerium oxide nanoparticles as an additive in the biodiesel diesel blend without any engine modification. In the research paper titled “Performance and Emission Characteristics of a Diesel Engine Using Cerium Oxide Nanoparticle Blended Biodiesel Emulsion Fuel” by A. Anbarasu and A. Karthikeyan (A. Anbarasu and A. Karthikeyan, 2016); the researchers synthesized biodiesel emulsion fuel by emulsification technique comprising 83% canola biodiesel, 15% water, and 2% surfactants. The above-prepared biodiesel emulsion fuel was doped with cerium oxide at 50 ppm. They carried out experimentation on a constant-speed diesel engine to find out the performance and emission characteristics. The brake thermal efficiency of nanoparticle blended fuel was higher than that of other tested fuels. The NO_x emissions have been significantly reduced for the biodiesel emulsion fuels compared with canola biodiesel. The NO_x emissions have been significantly reduced for the biodiesel emulsion fuels compared with canola biodiesel. The cerium oxide acts as an oxygen-donating medium that promotes the oxidation of carbon monoxide or absorbs oxygen for the decrease of nitrogen oxides. In this article titled “Influence of Zinc oxide on Direct Injection CI Engine Fueled

With Waste Cooking Oil Biodiesel” by Ashley Lobo, D K Ramesha, and Manjunath (Ashley Lobo *et al*, 2019); the researchers synthesized biodiesel from the cooking oil. This was blended with ZnO nanoparticles at a dosage of 80 ppm. Then the performance and emission parameters of conventional diesel, diesel blended with biofuel obtained from cooking oil in the ratio 80:20 by volume (B20) and B20 blended with ZnO nanoparticles are tested using a Kirloskar made TV2 diesel engine. From the experimentation, it was found that the NO_x emissions were reduced by 14% for the B20 blend and 16% for the B20+ZnO blend as compared to that of the diesel. It was also found that at full load conditions the CO emissions decrease by nearly 30% for both the blends B20 and B20+ZnO at full load as compared to the baseline reading of diesel. There was a decrease of 12% of the Brake Specific Fuel Consumption of the B20+ZnO blend because Zinc Oxide acts as an oxidizing agent and improves the overall combustion process. Smoke opacity falls by 3% when compared to the baseline reading of diesel at full load because of the improved surface-area-to-volume ratio of ZnO which increases the cetane number and thereby causes complete combustion.

In the paper titled “Effect of alumina nano additives into biodiesel-diesel blends on the combustion performance and emission characteristics of a diesel engine with exhaust gas recirculation” by Praveen Anchupogu, Lakshmi Narayana Rao, and Balakrishna Banavathu (Praveen Anchupogu *et al.*, 2018); the researchers have blended diesel with the biodiesel obtained from *Calophyllum inophyllum* in the ratio 80:20 (B20). Aluminum Oxide nanoparticles are blended with B20 in a dosage of 40 ppm. The experiments were conducted on a single-cylinder diesel engine with the diesel, CIB20, 20% of *Calophyllum inophyllum* biodiesel + 80% of diesel + 40 ppm Al₂O₃ nanoparticles (CIB20ANP40), CIB 20 + 20% exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), and CIB20ANP40 + 20% EGR fuel samples at different load conditions. The experimentation found out that NO_x emissions were reduced with the addition of alumina nanoparticles to the CIB20 fuel by 7.76% compared to the CIB20 fuel. The combined effect of alumina nanoparticles and EGR on the CIB20 fuel NO_x emissions decreased by 36.84% compared to the CIB20 fuel. After going through various research papers on biofuels blended with nanoparticles like cerium oxide, aluminum oxide, and zinc oxide; we have come to the conclusion that cerium oxide is the best nanoparticle that can be doped with diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio of 80:20 by volume. The addition of cerium oxide can significantly reduce NO_x emissions significantly.

8. Conclusion

The study on chemical and thermal properties of hemp methyl ester has been found out using the Biodiesel Analyzer software. We have obtained the performance and emission parameters for Diesel, B-100 (Pure Hemp Methyl Ester) and Diesel Blended With Hemp Methyl Ester Blended In The Ratio 80:20 By Volume (B-20).

8.1 Inferences Drawn

The following inferences were drawn from the experimentation. They are as follows:

- I. Biodiesel obtained from non-edible oils can be used as a suitable replacement for conventional diesel in heavy-duty vehicles.
- II. Despite having impeccable performance parameters, pure hemp methyl ester cannot be used as a suitable replacement for diesel in heavy-duty vehicles because of its high Carbon dioxide and oxides of nitrogen emission.
- III. Diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio of 80:20 by volume has a balance in parameter both performance and emission analysis. Therefore it can be a suitable replacement for diesel in heavy-duty vehicles.
- IV. It has been found out that a CI engine test rig using diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio of 80:20 by volume has a slightly higher NO_x as compared to that of a CI engine test conventional diesel.
- V. The higher NO_x emissions from diesel blended with hemp methyl ester in the ratio of 80:20 by volume can be reduced by a suitable dosage of Cerium dioxide nanoparticles.

8.2 Scope of Future Work

- I. We can add different types of nanoparticle and nano additives to diesel blended with biofuels and analyze their impact on the performance and emission parameters.
- II. This work shall be a source of inspiration to execute the work on a larger scale for the benefit of society.

- III. Through our work, we would like to tell the world about the importance of biofuels in sustainable transportation to combat the unprecedented crisis of climate change.
- IV. An extension for the near future is that alternate forms of fuels will be used extensively and biodiesel would be on the rise. Wide research on economic and environmental parameters would certainly increase its applications.

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